

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

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Description of the deliverable

The deliverable elaborates how the RECAP software components are developed and integrated. Localized versions of the platform are available in order to ensure their easier usage by both public administration servants and farmers with no knowledge of foreign languages.

Glossary

API	Application programming interface
BPS	Basic Payment Scheme
CC	Cross Compliance
JWT	Json Web Token
LPIS	Land Parcel Identification System
MD5	Hash function algorithm
NDVI	Normalised Difference Vegetation Index
NDWI	Normalised Difference Water Index
OCR	Optical character recognition
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
PA	Paying agency
PRSI	Plant Senescence Reflectance Index
RGB	Red Green Blue colour model
SAVI	Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index
SDK	Software development kit
Sen2Cor	Processor of Sentinel-2
TMS	Tile Map Service
WMS	Web Map service
WMTS	Web Map Tile Service

1 Introduction

Although the RECAP platform is still under development, a big part of the application has already been developed according to the user needs. This deliverable aims at describing the various components of the RECAP platform and explaining how these are being implemented as well as how they communicate with each other. There are five different components as these were described in the DOA:

1. The workflow component
2. The spatial component
3. The remote sensing component
4. The extractor component
5. The SDK

Each component is independent to each other and developed in such way, that changing or replacing one will not affect the rest of the system, helping towards building a scalable, modular and easy to maintain platform. Furthermore, should a need to add a new component arise, it will be easy to integrate it with the rest of the system without much effort based on the flexible communication channels that have already been established. In the following chapters, we get in more details about each component.

In order to make it easier for the reader, a small description of the system architecture taken from deliverable 3.1 is included here. The RECAP system can be logically described in three layers corresponding to:

- a) data layer: is responsible for gathering and storing all the data
- b) middleware layer: is where all the business logic lives and where the connection between the Data and the Frontend layers made possible
- c) the front-end parts of the system: is the medium through which the users interact with the system.

An overall architecture diagram as it was envisioned in deliverable 3.1, is presented below:

Figure 1: RECAP system architecture diagram

2 Workflow component

The workflow component is probably the most important part of the system in a sense that it acts as the link between the different parts of the system. Specifically, it brings together information that is processed by all components to the user in an easy to understand way. It functions as an orchestrator for the RECAP business logic, the communication with the data storage, the API, the receipt of information from outside sources and the validation process.

There are three different user roles within the system:

1. The farmer role
2. The inspector role
3. The paying agency role

2.1 Farmers

2.1.1 Filling in the farm details

One main responsibility of this component is to gather all the needed farm-related data from the users in order to further process it and provide them with meaningful information. This required data is the same data needed for the completion of the Basic Payment Scheme application. Based on users' input, the system can decide which cross compliance rules apply to their fields. Figure 2 presents a screenshot of the BPS form. The required information is split in steps so the users to enter the data in an easier way without getting lost in extremely long lists.

BPS

Step 1 Step 2 Step 3 Step 4 Step 5

Step 6 Step 7 Step 8 Step 9 Step 10 Step 11

You haven't created Organic application

Create a new BPS

Farmer's personal name: <input type="text" value="Enter farmers name"/>	Farmer's personal lastname: <input type="text" value="Enter farmers lastname"/>
Contact person for organic farming: <input type="text" value="Enter contact person"/>	Farmer's address: <input type="text" value="Enter farmers address"/>
Farmer's town: <input type="text" value="Enter farmers town"/>	Farmer's municipality: <input type="text" value="Enter farmers municipality"/>
Postal code of residence: <input type="text" value="Enter 5 digit number"/>	Farmer's personal tax number: <input type="text" value="Enter 10 digit number"/>
Farmer's telephone: <input type="text" value="Enter farmers telephone"/>	Farmer's personal fax number: <input type="text" value="Enter farmers fax number"/>
Farmer's farm identification number: <input type="text"/>	Farmer's personal web site: <input type="text"/>

Figure 2: Filling in the farm profile

On the final step the user is able to correlate each parcel (from the ones that have been declared in Step 1) with specific CC rules. This helps in case the user owns more than one parcels so that they don't not have to enter the same information multiple times depending on the number of parcels they own.

Questionnaire

Organic farming	Mark box if true	Relevant parcels
Do you have at least 0.01ha of the farm in the water protection zone?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have at least 0.01ha of the farm in the areas sensitive for erosion?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have have state kept botanical heritage objects in your declared area or have at least 0.01 ha of the farm in Natura 2000 sites?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have at least one type of these animals: horses, sheep, cattle, goats, ducks, mink, bison, fallow deer, turkeys, pigs, martens, foxes, mouffons, ostrich, bison, chinchilla, rabbits, chickens, geese?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Is at least 0.01 ha of the farm in Natura 2000 sites?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Are you a food (milk, honey, eggs) producer?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have pigs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have cattle?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have sheep and/or goat?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have (or will have in the future) calves?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have at least one animal (except pigeons, snails, earthworms, roe deers, bisons, wild boars, wolves, lynxes, bears, owls, swan, coon, parrots, skunk, elks, hares, hawk, zebras, capercaillie, camels, other pets, pumas)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>

Figure 3: Correlating parcels with CC rules

For each rule the user can select the parcel button and can then choose only the parcels to which the rule applies.

Select parcels relevant to the question: Do you have at least 0.01ha of the farm in the water protection zone?

Parcel name	Parcel ID	Mark relevant box
DA LI OVO RADII DDDD	279	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
test	1244	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
aa	aa	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
test2	2222	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
test	test	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 4: Selecting parcels

2.1.2 Cross compliance rules

A list of all the relevant rules is displayed to the end users, in order to simplify the visualization and grouping for complex regulations that the user needs to be compliant. Users can go through each rule and read the specific instructions on what they have to do in order to comply. To accommodate this, a checklist is supplied where the user can mark the completed instructions. Based on their answers, the rule is marked as complete or not (colour coded) so the user can visually identify fast what they still have to do in order to comply. Finally, users can attach relevant documents to each of the rules, if needed.

Figure 5: Cross compliance rules list

By selecting the “I” option at the top right of the CC rules page (red marked circle at the figure above), the users can view the inspection results grouped per CC rule along with any supportive documents that the inspectors have uploaded.

Must do						
Tasks	Comments	Documents	Images	Date	Time	Checked
Store manure and (or) slurry in the barn or to have a special storage (manure storage, slurry storage or thick manure pile) with appropriate capacity (not less than 6 months manure) near the barn.	0 comments	0 files	0 images			<input type="checkbox"/>
Have fertilization plan.	0 comments	0 files	0 images			<input type="checkbox"/>

Must NOT do						
Tasks	Comments	Documents	Images	Date	Time	Checked
Spread manure	0 comments	0 files	0 images			<input type="checkbox"/>
Store manure and (or) slurry in the barn or to have a special storage (manure storage, slurry storage or thick manure pile) with appropriate capacity (not less than 6 months manure) near the barn.	0 comments	0 files	0 images			<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 6: Cross compliance rule details

In order to gain an overview of their “obligations”, users can click the self-assessment button at the top left of the CC rules page and retrieve a total summary of what they should do and which documents are still missing.

2.1.3 Greening calculator

Another functionality of the workflow component is the greening calculator. If the user has added sub parcels via the spatial component, then through the CC rules page they can select the greening calculator and can check if they are compliant with the greening rules.

2.1.4 Farmers Log / Farmer Inspection

In order to assist users during an imminent inspection, the option to maintain input/output and work diary records was added in RECAP, which can help the farmer retrieve notes and details from the practices, that can prove helpful in case of an inspection.

Figure 7: Farmer's input log

The component was enriched with a document management tool, through which the users can upload documents and photos that can be mandatory for an imminent inspection, or can simply be used as proof of compliance to a specific rule. Documents can be attached to a rule, task or parcel and can be tagged so that users can easily find them again.

Figure 8: Uploading documents

During the inspection process, users can choose to make themselves visible to the inspectors and supply them access to documents, inputs/outputs and work diary records. User data are maintained securely on the RECAP servers and always remain private to their owners, unless granted to be shared with the inspectors.

2.1.5 Communication between farmers and PAs/Inspectors

The workflow was developed to allow the communication between the PAs/inspectors and farmers. Farmers can communicate directly with the PAs and ask them specific questions and the PAs can reply. Furthermore, inspectors can reach out to the farmer to ask for specific information before the inspection.

2.1.6 Notifications

Notifications/reminders are an important functionality of the workflow component and can be categorized in three different types:

- Reminders based on calendar key dates that the users must remember.
- Notifications/alerts based on the results from the remote sensing process. In case a non-compliance is detected for a specific rule, users are alerted and they gain visibility and access to the same information that inspectors have.
- Users can create their own custom reminders that will be displayed either as a calendar, or as a notification along with the calendar key dates reminders.

Figure 9: Reminders

2.1.7 User roles

Users can grant access to their accounts to other users, by defining role and access level. For instance, in some cases users may want to transfer ownership of their account to a consultant or farm staff so as to start working with their data.

Figure 10: User roles

2.2 Inspectors

The PAs are able to add an inspector. The inspectors are able to load all the relevant checklists and the maps for the farmer that will inspect in order to get ready for the inspection and help them make a decision on whether the farmer is compliant with the regulations or not.

Moreover, the inspectors can schedule an inspection through the scheduler and the farmer receives an email that contains the date that they will be notified about the coming inspection. A notification is also displayed within the farmer's app.

The screenshot shows the 'Scheduler' interface for 'test_gr@example.com'. It features a calendar for July 2017 with dates 7 and 14 highlighted. Below the calendar is a table titled 'Scheduler (4 added)' with the following data:

Line	Description	Date of the event	Date to be reminded
1	123	2017-07-21	2017-07-21

Figure 11: Scheduling an inspection

Based on the farmer's BPS application, the respective checklists are displayed to the inspector. In addition, some of the checklist fields get prepopulated based on the information provided by the farmer, saving valuable time for the inspector and minimising the possibility of entering wrong information.

Final decision | Schedule Inspection | CCRules Checklist | Log History

Step 1 | Step 2 | Step 3 | Step 4 | Step 5 | Step 6 | Step 7 | Step 8 | Step 9 | Step 10

Step 11 | Step 12 | Step 13 | Step 14 | Step 15 | Step 16 | Step 17 | Step 18 | Step 19 | Step 20

Step 21 | Step 22 | Step 23 | Step 24 | Step 25 | Step 26 | Step 27

Add sheep goats part 1

Holding code:

Location:

Digital spot:

Digital number:

Municipality:

Start date:

End date:

Figure 12: Inspection checklist

Once the inspector fills in all the checklists with the relevant information, they can go to the “final decision” page, by selecting the option on the top left. There they can define for each rule whether it is being followed by the farmer or not. When this task is finished, they can submit the final decision to the RECAP platform and a reporting email will be sent to the farmer and the PA.

GAEC 7a : Boundaries	PENDING	
GAEC 7c : Trees	PENDING	0
SMR 1 : Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZs)	PENDING	4
SMR 2 : Wild birds	BREACH DETECTED	2
SMR 4 : Food and feed law	PENDING	4
SMR 5 : Restrictions on the use of substances having hormonal or thyrostatic action and beta-agonists in farm animals	PENDING	0
SMR 6 : Pig identification and registration	PENDING	0
SMR 7 : Cattle identification and registration	PENDING	0
SMR 8 : Sheep and goat identification	PENDING	0
SMR 9 : Prevention and control of transmissible spongiform encephalopathies (TSEs)	PENDING	0
SMR 10 : Plant Protection Products (PPPs)	PENDING	0
SMR 11 : Welfare of calves	PENDING	0
SMR 12 : Welfare of pigs	PENDING	0
SMR 13 : Animal welfare	PENDING	0
None : None	PENDING	

[Submit Final Decision](#)

Figure 13: Final decision

By selecting the CC rules checklist button they can also view which rules apply to the farmers and request from them to share their data. Once the farmers respond to this request, the inspectors will gain visibility to the farmers' documents, work diary and input/output tables.

Finally, the inspectors can take and upload photos through their mobile app. These photos can be used as a proof to their final decision.

2.3 Paying Agencies

Through the workflow component, the PAs can supply access to other "inspector" users and assign to them farmers that should be inspected.

2.4 Technical implementation

The Workflow Component is mainly developed using the [Django Rest Framework](#) (DRF). DRF is a Django package (written in Python) with a powerful and flexible toolkit for building Web APIs. There are two types of API endpoints:

1. country specific API endpoints
2. common API endpoints

The country specific API endpoints are used in cases when there is no similarity in the CAP procedures between pilot countries, mainly happening in the farm profile creation and in the inspection section. In both cases, for every pilot country, different data is collected and they remain private to that pilot.

Every pilot country has a specific API root for the cross-compliance related activities, (e.g. for the UK it is *bps_uk*) and all of the API endpoints related to these activities for the specific pilot are on the same root.

The Common API endpoints are used for the functionalities which are common for all of the pilot countries (e.g. document management, reminders/notifications, etc.).

The [JSON Web Token](#) (JWT) standard is used to ensure security of the data. JWT is an open standard (RFC 7519) that defines a compact and self-contained way for securely transmitting information between parties as a JSON object. Every user gets his/her own JWT on login and it is sent to the API endpoint every time through the HTTP header for safely retrieval of the data. JWT is reseted every half an hour. After that time, if user is away from the RECAP application, he/she will be automatically logged out. Implementation of JWT authentication is done using the following package [djangorestframework-jwt](#).

DRF permissions are implemented in order to manage access to the API endpoints to:

- the users from different countries
- the users with different role on specific account (Edit, Read Only or Upload Document role)
- the different type of users (PAs, inspectors, farmers)

Every time a user with unauthorized access tries to get, post or update the data, or invalid data are sent to the server, an error message will be raised.

All of the data are stored in one centralized [PostgreSQL](#) database. Based on the user account, the pilot country where he/she is from and also the API endpoint, the user will get the data from the specific table from the DB. Also, data will be filtered and the user will be able to retrieve only the data related to his/her account.

For the purpose of managing documents, [Mayan EDMS](#) is used. Mayan EDMS is a Free Open Source Electronic Document Management System, coded in the Python language using the Django web application framework. It's RESTful API part is adapted to the needs of the RECAP. All of the documentation uploaded by users like photos, pdfs, docs etc. is stored in a centralized File System. Every document gets its own system generated name and an access link for the document is saved in the PostgreSQL DB. Storing and accessing the documentation is performed by the Restful API of the Mayan EDMS.

Searching and filtering the data is implemented using DRF filters. Mayan EDMS has a feature for automatic OCR processing which is used for the easy search of the documents' content.

Notifications and reminders are handled by [Celery](#). Celery is an asynchronous task queue based on distributed message passing, also written in Python. Celery is set to check every 5 seconds if there is any notification or reminder to be shown. If there is, Celery changes the visibility of notifications/reminders and they will be shown to the users. In the same time, Celery triggers `django.core.mail` module to automatically send an email with an explanation of the notification/reminder.

3 Spatial component

3.1 PAs and Inspectors

The Spatial component provides PA officers and inspectors access to the spatial information generated by the Remote Sensing component and external spatial data. With the use of maps the users are able to visualize information needed for the selection and inspection process. Specifically, they are able to view maps containing information about:

- Time-series of Sentinel-2 background optical imagery for viewing only
- Habitat
- Natura sites,
- Nitrate Vulnerable Zones,
- Botanical Heritage Sites
- Watercourse maps
- Slope map (or DEM)
- Administrative boundaries and settlements
- Land Use / Land Cover Maps, as detailed as possible
- ILOT and sub-ILOT
- LPIS (WMS or shp)
- Remote sensing alerts

The remote sensing component results are also displayed in the form of map controls in the user interface.

This information can be used by the Paying Agency as auxiliary information in their risk analysis process and identify the farmers that are more likely not to comply, so that they may get inspected. Specifically the PAs are able to select a bounding box on the map from the area that they are interested in, which triggers the remote sensing processes and returns the results of the Remote sensing analysis.

On the other hand, the inspectors have access to this information before and during an inspection so that they can prove to a farmer on breaches detected by Remote Sensing and also identify non-compliance when on the spot.

3.2 Farmers

The Spatial component is also used by the farmers in the following ways:

- They are able to insert their fields to the system, by drawing the shape over a map. Later this shape will be also editable in case something went wrong, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 14: Adding parcel geometry

- They have access to some of the maps mentioned above.
- They have access to the Remote sensing results.

3.3 Technical implementation

Spatial data can be divided into three groups:

1. User-generated spatial data
2. Static spatial data
3. Background layers

The user-generated spatial data includes parcel boundaries and location of geotagged photos. The geometry of these data is stored in [PostGIS/PostgreSQL](#) DB. PostGIS is a spatial database extender for the PostgreSQL object-relational database. It adds support for geographic objects allowing location queries to run in SQL. Geometry in PostGIS is stored as one additional column. Creating, updating and deleting the geometry is performed using [djangorestframework-gis](#) package. This package relies on DRF, Django's spatial extension Geodjango and [GDAL](#) (Geospatial Data Abstraction Library), a geospatial library for the translation and manipulation of geospatial - raster and vector - data. The results are returned in GeoJSON, a suitable format for adding these data on the map.

Static spatial data like Habitat, Nitrate Vulnerable Zones, Slope map (or DEM), Land Use, etc. are available through WMS OGC service via UMN Mapserver and MapProxy.

The main purpose of the background layers is to be used as base layer (background) for drawing the shapes of the farmer's fields. As background layer, Bing Maps (Aerial with roads) are used and

displayed via OGC WMS. This is not a strict solution, other background WMS layers could be used also.

All of the above mentioned spatial data, user-generated spatial data, static spatial data and background layers are together presented in form of map using OpenLayers (see RECAP interface).

4 Extractor component

The extractor component is aimed at the PA officers only. It is responsible to extract valuable information from the RECAP database in order to uncover patterns that allow officers to revise their policies. After communicating with the PAs to find out what it is that they need in terms of reporting information, they come back with the following items that are offered through the extractor component:

- How many farmers have used the system, per region?
- Which rules are the ones that farmers fail to follow the most?
- Which parts of the system have they used?
- How often does each farmer use the system and in which item?
- Which operation system/ devices are being used the most?

The aforementioned items combined are used to extract all the information that Paying Agencies need, in order to perform more targeted inspections and get insights on whether the farmers' responded correctly to the cross compliance rules.

4.1 Technical implementation

The Extractor component is based on a Business Intelligence (BI) system like [SpagoBI visualizing and analyzing RECAP information](#). Extractor component makes use of all of the data stored in PostGIS/PostgreSQL DB, from all of the components, in order to extract the desired statistics.

5 Remote sensing (RS) component

The basic functionality of the component is to provide Remote Sensing products, including image classification derivatives and vegetation indices, as well as RGB satellite images, using a set of Sentinel 2 images. Particularly, the RS component, based on an incoming Area of Interest (AOI – bounding box of a geometry) and a declared land parcel dataset, proceeds with the execution of the following processes:

- Searching Sentinel 2 products (L1C or L2A) for the specified AOI from the Sentinels Scientific Data Hub and selecting the satellite images with the minimum cloud cover for each month.
- Downloading Sentinel 2 products and verifying the product integrity using MD5 checksum.
- Preprocessing Sentinel 2 products, including a series of time consuming geospatial processes as it is described below:

- Performing atmospheric, terrain and cirrus correction of L1C products using the *Sen2Cor* processor and producing L2A products, namely, Bottom-of-Atmosphere corrected reflectance images.
- *Resampling* each band to a higher spatial resolution (10m) and *Converting* to GeoTIFF raster files.
- *Transforming* each band to the Spherical Mercator projection coordinate system EPSG: 3857 and *Mosaicing* each band-tile per month as well *Subsetting-Clipping* to the specified AOI.
- *Producing* RGB satellite images and vegetation indices, such as NDVI, NDWI, PSRI, SAVI.
- *Creation of Feature Space*, based on a stack of all Sentinel 2 bands and extracting the average of spectral values of each overlaid land parcel with each band
- Classifying Sentinel 2 products, providing the estimated crop type, family type and season, for each parcel. This process is intended to address Greening rules.
Executing a water pollution Risk Assessment modeling process, towards addressing SMR1 and GAEC1 and GAEC 5 rule.
- Estimating crop burning residues to check compliance for GAEC 6.
- Publishing RGB satellite images and/or indices, creating a WMS service.
- Updating RECAP platform with RS results.

Upon request from the PA by defining an AOI, the Remote Sensing component returns for each parcel included in the AOI the following information:

Cross-compliance checks with RS and attributes per parcel

Attribute code	Attribute description	Attribute type
Green1	Diversification of crops	Boolean (checked or not checked)
Green2	Maintainance of permanent grassland	Boolean (checked or not checked)
GAEC4	Minimum Soil Cover	Boolean (checked or not checked)
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	Float
PSRI	Plant senescence reflectance index	Float
SAVI	Soil-adjusted vegetative index	Float
SeasType	Seasonal Label Estimation	String (summer, winter, permanent)
FamType	Crop Family Label Estimation	String
CropType	Lowest level of crop specificity	Integer (from lookup table)
GAEC6	Crop residue burning residues	Boolean (checked or not checked)
BurnPerc	Percentage of the parcel that is burnt	Float
BurnTimestamp	Month of the year for which the the burned area was mapped	Integer
SMR1	Water pollution risk assessment – Risk Indicator	Boolean (checked or not checked)
GAEC 1	Comply with buffer zones	Boolean (checked or not checked)
GAEC 5	Soil Erosion/Poor tillage	Boolean (checked or not checked)
Slope	Average parcel slope angle	Float (decimal degrees)
Aspect	Average parcel aspect angle	Float (decimal degrees)
K-factor	Soil erosivity depended on the the ground composition (clay, sandy, etc.)	Float
C-factor	Soil erosivity according to land/cover and tillage practices	Float
SoilErIndx	Product of K-factor and C-factor	Float
RUSLE	Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation	Float
WaterProx	Distance between parcel and closest watercourse	Float
Risk index	Parcel risk assessment for water pollution	String (V. Low, Low, Medium, High, V. High)

This information is then combined with auxiliary data and used within the RECAP platform to provide indications about specific CC rules.

5.1 Technical implementation

The RS component has been built using purely open source technologies and standards. The Python programming language and more specifically **Django**, a high level python web framework, is the main development tool along with additional libraries like **GDAL**.

Django uses the MVC (Model – View – Controller) standard design pattern which separates the logic from representation and provides a modular pythonic way to develop reusable applications. The RS component makes use of the **Django Rest Framework** (DRF), in order to supply a list of appropriate endpoints for the seamless interaction with the RECAP platform. JWT is used in order to generate tokens and verify the user who is calling one of the protected API endpoints. Moreover, the RS component uses the **GeoDjango** package in order to enhance the system with GIS functionalities and capabilities.

GDAL is the basic tool for reading and writing spatial data while the **NumPy** and **SciPy** libraries (Python packages for scientific computing) offer remarkable capabilities for the manipulation of multi-dimensional arrays (eg raster resampling / converting) and the implementation of linear algebra and complex mathematical algorithms.

Additionally, the RS component makes use of:

- The **OSSIM** geospatial package, a suite of advanced image processing utilities written in Python, for the mosaic production and raster transformation.
- ESA's **Sen2Cor** processor, an important geospatial package for the production of atmospheric corrected satellite images.
- **Matlab**, for the image classification process as it constitutes the basic development environment of the classification algorithms and data production.

Execution of geoprocessing tasks:

- **Celery** and **RabbitMQ Server Message broker**, a message-oriented middleware that implements the Advanced Message Queuing Protocol and is necessary for the receiving and sending messages, for the execution of geo-processing tasks.

Publication of geospatial data:

- **UMN MapServer** and **MapProxy** for the creation of OGC Services (Web Map Service, Web feature Service) and caching, respectively. Specifically, UMN Mapserver is an open source geographic data rendering engine written in C and is indicated for serving large geospatial datasets, both, raster and vector, according to OGC web mapping standards. MapProxy is an open source geospatial proxy and tile server, fully compliant with WMS, WMS-C, WMTS and TMS services.

Management and storing of geospatial data:

- **PostgreSQL** Database Management System in conjunction with its spatial extension, **PostGIS** for the management and storing of geospatial data. Django/GeoDjango is fully compatible with Postgres/PostGIS.
- The **Apache** web server, a widespread open source software, is connected to Django application in order to serve the RS Web API and respond to RESTful requests (GET, POST, PUT, PATCH, DELETE).

6 SDK component

A software development kit is being developed on top of the RECAP REST API, providing a wrapper over the API, so that it can assist developers and agricultural consultants develop their own custom applications that will extend RECAP functionality. It offers all of RECAP functionalities and more specifically it gives the possibility to:

- Search RECAP data
- Integrate search results into their applications.
- Present a custom UI
- Manage RECAP configuration and objects
- Log in directly to RECAP

Figure 15: SDK

The RECAP SDK is offered in the Python programming language, but developed using a clear approach based on API calls and simple logic, so it can be easily copied to be ported to other languages by developers. It follows an easily readable coding style, a modular object-oriented architecture and clean documentation with code samples to demonstrate how the different functions can be used.

As described in D3.1 RECAP system architecture, the RECAP SDK consists of three main modules:

6.1 Authentication module

When using the SDK, users must authenticate against the central RECAP authentication JWT (JSON WebToken) mechanism before they can use the rest of the service. The SDK keeps the returned JWT token in memory for the duration of the active SDK process run, offering a ready for

use valid token to subsequent core services. Any core SDK function seeks for a “in memory” token, before being able to perform its business target. If a token is not found, the authentication module is responsible to handle expired tokens triggering the authentication cycle again when needed. In order for the SDK to receive a token, the developer needs to authenticate via a valid username and password. Important part of the Authentication component is the configuration file where developers will need to enter their credentials once, during the installation process of the RECAP SDK into their development environment.

6.2 Core Services Module

The main SDK functions will be called in accordance to the ones in the RECAP REST API described above. A bundle of methods of the Core Services Class will be responsible to implement the appropriate calls from the SDK to the REST API, offering a suitable way to the developers to integrate their systems directly with RECAP. As mentioned, the RECAP SDK calls need to use an active JWT token in order to be verified against the RECAP platform and be allowed to perform the essential actions. This requires a close connection between the Core Services Module and the Authentication Module, by maintaining an Authentication instance inside Core Services, offering authentication control to all SDK services.

Finally, the Core Services will implement the Singleton pattern in order to avoid multiple connections (and multiple tokens) with the RECAP server during the same process. Due to this pattern, the module will be responsible to handle error exceptions or connectivity and timeout issues which occur from the SDK or the API centrally.

6.3 Converter Module

Converter is the module which will be responsible to convert the API responses to the appropriate SDK objects based on the programming language version of the RECAP SDK (Python only for the beginning). It will also be responsible to convert SDK objects to POST parameters according to the needs of the API's endpoint.

7 Overall technical implementation and integration practices

7.1 Localisation

During the pilot operations, the platform will be used in 5 different countries and hence there was a need for a clear localisation mechanism. Every pilot country will be able to use the RECAP platform both in English and the country's native language. The RECAP platform is automatically translated to the specific language based on the language chosen in the user profile.

There are three types of data that should be translated within RECAP platform:

- Attributes residing in the RECAP Database:

For every column that should be translated, there is a corresponding column with the prefix *tr_**. Every API call makes use of the Accept-Language parameter in the HTTP header which upon receipt, it will be processed and the respective translated column from the database will be returned.

- Emails, validation errors and exceptions in Python code: Django provides utilities to extract the translation strings into a message file by using Python's standard library (*gettext*). The message file is a convenient way for translators to provide the translated text in the target language. Like above, using the Accept-Language parameter in the HTTP header, strings marked for translation will be matched and returned to the desired language.
- Frontend text: [angular-gettext](#) library, similar to the Django gettext utilities, will be used for the translation of the frontend text resources.

7.2 *Integration between the RECAP components and the RECAP interface*

All RECAP components are developed through one backend application as all of them function upon the same data. Because of that, it is hard to separate one from the others. The RECAP components are different functional units all working under the RECAP platform roof, through a common user interface.

The platform interface and front-end logic is written using [AngularJS](#) framework, as a suitable implementation of the client-side MVC pattern. The application is divided into modular AngularJS components, each representing a logical part of the platform. Apart from AngularJS components, there is an independent "helper" javascript file, which contains all the API endpoints. These API URLs are accessible to all AngularJS components.

At the very top of the platform structure, there is a root AngularJS component. It is used for several tasks like:

- Handling initial state of the application - e.g. checking if the user is authenticated and depending on the response, it redirects the user to either the login page or the desired component.
- Handling transition and communication between AngularJS components, using Angular UI Router. For example, every step in the Farm profile is a different component, so whenever the user clicks "Next", UI Router handles the transition to the next step and all of the data that needs to be passed alongside the transition.
- Injecting all the third-party AngularJS modules, services and directives, that are being used in the application.

All of the AngularJS components use the same database system, but on the client side, the platform organizes these components into categories:

- Country-specific AngularJS components - e.g. farm profile is different for every country. Hence, every country has its own farm profile component and corresponding subcomponents. The same idea is applied to the work diary section as well.

- User-specific AngularJS components – The platform decides which components are enabled for a user, based on the type of user. For example, an inspector has his/her own dashboard, his/her own inspector profile, sidebar etc.
- Common AngularJS components - all other components, that are common to all types of users and countries.

When the user logs in to the platform, information about his/her account, role, permissions, language, etc. is stored in a cookie. Based on that, the RECAP platform can identify the user and control what information he/she can access. Using this mechanism, the system can allow the user to perform certain operations or restrict access to specific parts of the platform based on their role and assigned permissions.

The Spatial component is implemented using OpenLayers (javascript library for map and spatial data visualization). This component can be divided into 3 parts:

- Visualization - user-generated spatial data, parcels/sub-parcels and bounding boxes, retrieved via REST API in GeoJSON data format. Background layers (e.g. Bing maps) and static spatial data are displayed using OGC WMS standard.
- Functionalities - depending on the user type (farmer, inspector or paying agency), different types of map functionalities are available. For example, farmer can use draw, select and delete action to manage parcel/sub-parcel geometry, but paying agency user can use only draw action to create bounding boxes.
- Data service - A custom AngularJS service is created to handle geometry data exchange between components. The PAs are using this service, to send the bounding box geometry to the Remote Sensing component and the farmers are using this service to store parcels and sub-parcels into the database.

Extractor component communicates with the RECAP platform via REST API in the same way as all of the SDK tools.

The communication between RS component and RECAP platform is achieved through the developed RESTful Web API endpoints and the REST API of DRF and OGC services via UMN Mapserver and MapProxy as this was described in deliverable D3.1.

Figure 16: Communication between RS and RECAP systems

As it is indicated in the diagram above, the RECAP platform makes a POST request (1) to the RS system. The request is triggered by the Spatial component, sending a specified Area of Interest (AOI) - a geometry in GeoJSON format. This area of interest is defined by the PA, while drawing the bounding box. After that, RS component triggers two parallel actions; a GET request (2) in order to retrieve and store land parcels that are contained in the above AOI and the execution of the required processes (3) as these were described in the first section. When the execution of the processes are completed, then RS component makes PATCH requests (4) in order to update the relative parcels with the RS results, which are then displayed to the end users through the Spatial and the workflow components.

8 Conclusions

This document describes the development of the RECAP components as these have been shaped based on the DoA and the user requirements. Work is still in progress and what is stated in this document is what we have been developed/decided so far. Based on the feedback that the team will receive on the next round of co-production workshops, there is a chance that some of the functionality described here, might change until the delivery of the first version of the platform.